

RADx-UP Working Groups Governance - Roles & Responsibilities

I. Purpose

The purpose of this process document is to outline the roles and responsibilities of Working Group (WG) members responsible for governance. The document provides a clear understanding of what each member’s responsibilities are, how they are expected to perform them and what outcomes are expected.

II. Scope

This document applies to all currently active RADx-UP Working Groups (including Community-Engaged WGs, Collective Impact Networks, and Scientific Taskforces). Successful implementation of these activities aim to facilitate collaboration that leads to the sharing of knowledge and development of resources (e.g., stories, experiences, tools/toolkits, techniques, etc.), strategies, and innovations that further advance the reach of community and project goals. This document outlines the following roles and responsibilities for WG chairs, governance committee members, group organizers, members, and expert advisors/guests.

Key Personnel	Description
Chair and Co-chairs (1-3 individuals)	These individual(s) are responsible for the overall management of the working group. They create a supportive and safe environment which fosters each participant’s ability to contribute fully and equally, enabling a shared, collaborative outcome. The WG chair/co-chairs are not simply symbolic leaders; the success of the initiative hinges on the commitment of the co-chairs to pitch in during and between meetings.
Governance Committee (1-5 individuals)	Comprised of workgroup members (1-5 individuals). As a community of practice (CoP), these groups should aim to be one of self-governance. A CoP is best served by a governance model that encourages power sharing and joint decision-making.
Workgroup Members	Members are responsible for actively participating in the meetings. They should contribute their expertise and knowledge to the group's discussions and decision making. Members are also responsible for carrying out any actions agreed upon during the meeting.
Group Organizer	This individual “owns” the charter of the group. They may have ideas about what the goals of the group should be, and how to reach them. This person helps the group stay focused on its particular group and helps provide solutions as issues arise.
Experts Advisors/Guests	Expert advisors are people who are called upon for their specific knowledge on a relevant topic. They are usually not members of the working group but are asked to provide advice and guidance to the group. For example, an invited expert might conduct a requested presentation. If this individual meets the CP compensation criteria then they can be eligible for the standard CP payment rate of \$100 per hour.

III. Responsibilities¹

It is the responsibility of all individuals involved with the RADx-UP Working Groups to ensure they are familiar with these processes outlined in this document. This section outlines who is **Responsible**, **Accountable**, and **Consulted** about Working Group related tasks, communications, and deliverables.

Working Group Leadership & Governance				
Task	WG Type	R	A	C
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributing to the development of the agenda and content for each WG meeting –including serving as thought partners to Backbone staff and helping contribute content expertise Facilitating discussions and decision making in meetings Provide overall guidance to CDCC support staff to facilitate progress toward WG goals Nurturing relationships among Working Group members Attend monthly WG Steering Committee Meeting – 4th Tuesday of each month at 1:30pm EST <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Escalate any challenges to the domain lead for guidance. The domain lead will escalate issues to CEC leadership for further discussion with NIH and CDCC leadership as needed. 	Community-engaged WGs	WG chair/co-chairs	WG chair/co-chairs	Domain Lead and/or CDCC staff
	Collective Impact Networks	Governance Committee	Governance Committee	
	Scientific Taskforces	Group Organizer	Group Organizer	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actively participate in the meetings Contribute their expertise and knowledge to the group's discussions and decision making Carry out any actions agreed upon during the meeting Represent the interests of their organization or group 	All Types	Workgroup Members		WG Lead
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide advice and guidance on a relevant topic Attend meetings when requested to do so Share their expertise and knowledge with the group Assist the group in making informed decisions. 	All Types	Expert Advisors/Guests		WG Lead

¹ **Responsible** (this team member does the work to complete the task), **Accountable** (this team member is ultimately responsible for the task. If work is delegated, the last one to review the task or deliverable), **Consulted** (the team members to be consulted prior to a final decision or action), and **Informed** (the team members who need to be informed on progress and decisions)

IV. Time Commitment

As a Working Group leader/member, you play a vital role in guiding your workgroup towards achieving its goals and objectives. However, this position can potentially require a significant time commitment to effectively facilitate meetings, communicate with members, and oversee the progress of your group's work.

Generally, you should expect to devote at least 2-3 hours per month to your duties as a Working Group leader (i.e. co-chair, governance committee member, or group organizer). This includes preparing and coordinating meeting agendas, facilitating discussions, and following up on action items. Additionally, you may need to spend time communicating with other members, stakeholders, or outside organizations to coordinate efforts and gather input.

Depending on the size and scope of your workgroup's work, you may also need to dedicate more time during certain periods or for specific tasks. For example, if your group is responsible for organizing a conference or event, you may need to commit additional hours for planning and logistics.

Ultimately, the success of your group's work will depend on your ability to effectively manage your time and balance your responsibilities as a WG leader with other professional and personal commitments. Clear communication, delegation of tasks, and a strong team dynamic can also help ensure that your group's goals are achieved while minimizing the time burden on individual members.

V. Review and Revision

This process will be reviewed as needed (more frequent review may be warranted as processes change or major edits are identified). Additional steps include checking link in the process document and reviewing all attachments.

All RADx-UP Program Manual documents are to be reviewed at least once a year.

VI. Attachments

List the numbers and titles of optional flowcharts or any other documents attached to this process. Attachments are to be added after the approval page.

- I. Types of Working Groups (see below)

Attachments

I. Types of RADx-UP Working Groups

WG TYPE	DESCRIPTION
<p>Community-engaged Working Groups (CE WG)</p> <p><i>Involve</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: A supportive space for professional exchange and support between RADx-UP projects that share an understanding of COVID-19 related problems. • Membership: RADx-UP academic and community partners • Roles: Chair/co-chair (1-3) and CDCC staff support (2) • Communication Channels: Email, Asana, and/or Slack channels • Compensation: Community partners earn \$150 per session. • Evaluation: WG identifies 1-3 goals to complete over a 12-month cycle. CDCC staff and co-chairs are responsible for the completion of the following: 1) 3-month activation template, 2) 6-month progress report, 3) 12-month progress report, 4) Bi-monthly feedback form, 5) 12-month WG member survey
<p>Collective Impact Networks (CIN)</p> <p><i>Shared Leadership</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: An informal space for ongoing professional exchange and support around a specific objective/focus. Cultivating shared ownership is essential for the sustainability of these networks. Once the WGs begin to take shape, transition from relying solely on the CDCC staff to relying on members to lead and manage group activities is encouraged. • Membership: RADx-UP (academic and community partners) + external partners + CDCC • Roles: These CoPs will identify and communicate the roles and responsibilities that will support their vision, mission, and growth. Roles may include Leader/Sponsor, Core Team Members, support teams (administration, operations), facilitators, moderators, content area experts, and others¹. • Communication Channel: LinkedIn Groups (social media platform) will enable WG members to communicate, organize and share leadership long-term and apart from RADx-UP staff support and structure to develop a sustainable community. • Compensation: No compensation • Evaluation: CDCC staff and the WG governance committee are responsible for the completion of the following: Group Charter slide deck
<p>Scientific Taskforces (ST)</p> <p><i>Collaborate</i></p>	<p>Short-term (1-3 months) task force established and organized around a singular SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound) goal. These nimble groups of project representatives can offer their expertise and experience to short-term processes (such as the development of CDEs, derived variables, analytic strategies and analysis proposals) that affect the projects.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Membership: RAD-UP (academic and community partners) + NIH + CDCC • Roles: Group Organizer, Core Team Members, Experts/Guests and CDCC staff support (+1) • Communication Channel: Email • Compensation: Depends (verify with domain lead) • Evaluation: CDCC staff and group organizer are responsible for the completion of the following: Group Charter slide deck